

Prediction of Covid-19 Infected Chest X-Rays Using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract- As the number of cases with COVID-19 continues to climb, better medical screening and clinical care of the condition are urgently needed. Typical signs of a chest cold include a sore throat, cough, and a high temperature. Patients with pneumonia also have these symptoms. Because of this, detecting COVID-19 is much more difficult. Recognizing COVID-19 in a set of Chest-X-Ray (CXR) pictures that also contains pneumonia patients is laborious and prone to human mistake. Radiography of the chest for COVID-19 cases and others with comparable symptoms may be used as a first-line triage method. While this is true, radiologists still have a hard time distinguishing between COVID-19 CXR pneumonia and other types of pneumonia due to the similarities in their appearance. This work is an effort to construct a machine learning model that is beneficial in categorizing CXR pictures into three classes indicating normal, COVID-9, and pneumonia based on the premise that such classifiers can consistently identify COVID-19 CXR images from other kinds of pneumonia. Feature The methods of extraction, dimensionality reduction, and machine learning are all used.

Index Terms- Chest X-Rays, Covid-19, Machine Learning, Prediction, Pneumonia.

I. INTRODUCTION

In December of 2019, a corona virus disease (COVID - 19) pandemic began in Wuhan, China and quickly spread over the globe. There is currently no cure or vaccination available for COVID -19. Severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus (also known as COVID-19) is the causative agent of the current COVID-19 pandemic. Worldwide, - 19) has infected millions and killed a number of people. The world's biggest issue is COVID-19. The epidemic has been labeled a "global health emergency" by the World Health Organization (WHO). The lungs are particularly vulnerable to Corona virus illness. Temperature elevation, dehydration, coughing, and other respiratory distress are among Corona virus symptoms. As a newly identified species in 2019, COVID-19 has not been tentatively connected to humans. Early evidence suggests that the symptoms caused by COVID-19 are milder than those caused by hepatitis C virus (HCV), which may range from moderate to life-threatening. Faster triage of non-COVID-19 patients and more efficient use of hospital resources for COVID-19 cases are both possible thanks to an accurate automated system for classifying CXR pictures according to the presence or absence of the COVID-19 virus. The reliable interpretation of medical pictures has been greatly aided by technologies founded in Machine Learning (ML). Methods that are based on machine learning are able to scale, be automated, and be easily used in practical situations. A typical task in ML-based image analysis is the categorization of photos having similar properties. To directly assign picture samples into target classes, this strategy focuses on segmenting the region of interest, identifying useful image features extracted from the segmented area in the spatial or frequency domain, and developing an optimum machine learning-based classification technique. Triage of individuals with comparable symptoms but not COVID-19 might begin with a chest X-ray (CXR). Classifiers trained with machine learning can consistently identify COVID-19 patients in CXR pictures by separating them from patients with other types of pneumonia. Feature extraction, a method of digital image processing, and dimensionality reduction, a method of machine learning, are used to develop a reliable machine learning classifier in this study, one that can accurately and sensitively identify COVID-19 cases from those without the virus. Literature review, suggested study, findings, and a conclusion make up the remainder of the article.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

New machine learning-based approaches for analysing COVID-19 medical pictures have been proposed. CT scans were used by Wang et al.[2] to construct a deep learning network, DenseNet121, that had previously been taught to categories using data from the COVID-19 imaging tests. In determining whether the data was positive or negative, 81.24 percent of the time, the prediction was correct. Prevention relies on identifying high-risk patients and putting available medical resources to the best use, and early diagnosis of COVID-19 is essential for this. Zhang et al. [3] recommended training on ResNet-18 for improved lung lesion segmentation in CT images. The accuracy of the classifier model is 92.49 percent for the combined pneumonia and normal COVID-19 categories. The study's goal was to determine whether or not combining spatial and frequency-domain imaging characteristics may better characterise tumour heterogeneity and predict tumour response to postoperative chemotherapy in patients with advanced-stage ovarian cancer. To begin, a computer-aided method was used to calculate 133 attributes. The characteristics were categorised into shape/density, fast Fourier transform, wavelet, discrete cosine transform (DCT), and grey level difference. The method relied on the particle swarm optimization technique to create a cluster of characteristics with the right amount of variation to accomplish better discrimination than was possible using any of the features individually.

Clinical data from 120 ovarian cancer patients was collected in a retrospective manner and used to evaluate the methodology. DCT features showed the highest prediction accuracy across all five groups when comparing individual feature findings. The best feature cluster produced a quantitative image marker with an area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.86, while the best single feature produced an AUC of just 0.74. Properties in the frequency domain were also shown to be important, alongside those in the spatial domain. In conclusion, this study's findings reveal that a combination of the proposed new quantitative image marker and features determined from the spatial and frequency domains might effectively predict the response of a tumour to chemotherapy after surgical removal.

CT imaging features of his novel virus are shown to be distinct from those of previously described viral pneumonias, as determined by Xu et al. They use a number of different CNN models for image classification in computed tomography to help in the early identification of COVID-19. A total of 618 CT images are obtained, from 175 healthy people, 219 COVID-19 infected patients, and 224 CT samples of influenza A virus pneumonia. They use a three-dimensional convolutional neural network (CNN) model based on the well-tested ResNet-18 network architecture to partition the possible image cubes. The author makes use of a system for classifying images in three dimensions in order to arrange all of the image blocks in the text. This categorization scheme was developed to help make sense of the connections seen in medical imaging of the lungs. The overall confidence score of CT cases and the specific infection type (COVID-19, influenza A viral pneumonia, or no infection diagnosed) are both calculated using noisy or Bayesian functions.

Shan et al. [9] propose a deep learning system they name "VB Net" to automatically segment and measure the corona virus-infected regions in computed tomography images. The VB Net model integrates features from both the V-Net and bottleneck models. While both the V-Net and the bottleneck model utilise convolution and down sampling to pull out broad picture characteristics, the bottleneck model further use convolution and up sampling to blend in more granular information. First, 249 people with COVID-19 were used to train the model, and then another 300 COVID-19 patients were used to verify it. To expedite the laborious task of displaying COVID-19 CT scans for training, the author offers a "in loop (HITL)" technique that iteratively generates training examples. After three iterations, the drawing time is reduced to 4 minutes using the proposed manual loop approach for updating the model. Using the Dice correspondence coefficient, we find that the deep learning model achieves 91.6% accuracy in subdividing the whole 300-verification-set.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

This project work carries the following steps to build a model that classifies the CXR image of a person who is either healthy or infected by COVID-19 or Pneumonia which is shown in Fig.1. It involves Collecting datasets, Data preprocessing, Feature extraction, Feature evaluation, Feature reduction, Model training and testing.

ALGORITHM

Step 1: Collecting Datasets

A collection of 420 CXR images [11,12] stored in three folders namely normal (indicating perfectly healthy person), covid (indicating covid infected person) and pneumonia (indicating pneumonia infected person) respectively.

STEP 2: DATA PREPROCESSING

Data preprocessing involves two steps. Min-Max normalization and Adaptive Histogram equalization. These two steps are applied for each image.

STEP3:FEATUREEXTRACTION

Five different types of features are extracted for each image, three types of spatial domain features and two types of frequency domain features. Spatial domain features are Texture, GLDM, GLCM and frequency domain features are FFT and Wavelet. The computed features are stored in a .mat file as a 420x252 array meaning 252 features for 420 images each.

STEP4:FEATUREEVALUATION

The computed features are then evaluated by calculating correlation matrix and histogram.

STEP5:FEATUREREDUCTION

The features are reduced from 252 to 64 features each using Kernel-PCA method.

STEP 6:MODEL TRAINING AND TESTING

A deep learning model with two hidden layers of 128 and 16 dimensions respectively is built. The data is loaded into the model and 60% is used for training and 20% for testing and 20% for validation.

Fig.1 Algorithm Flowchart

The results obtained are shown from Fig.2 to Fig.5.

CXR of a healthy person (Before)

CXR of a healthy person (After)

Fig.2 Output of Data Preprocessing

Fig.3 Histogram representation of correlation coefficients

Fig.4 Confusion Matrix

Fig.5 Graph comparing training loss (red line) and validation loss (blue line)

VI. CONCLUSION

A Model that classifies the Chest-X-Ray images into three classes namely covid, normal and pneumonia is built. Feature extraction and dimensionality reduction techniques are used. A relatively small dataset of 420 Chest-X-Ray images is considered. The overall accuracy of the model obtained is 94.05%. Machine learning models surely cannot replace the traditional and more accurate diagnosis systems, but the technological advancements happening everyday are making the ML models more and more accurate and reliable. This work attempts to build a reasonably accurate ML model that can be handy while performing the diagnosis of COVID-19 patients. Although the main limitation being consideration of a small dataset, this can be used as a reference to explore any other methods in constructing accurate and reliable Machine Learning models in the future.

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